

(2H, m, C-2' and C-6' H); MS: m/e 330 (M⁺), 315, 301, 287, 259, 231, 149, 135. Found: C, 62.11; H, 4.26. C₁₇H₁₄O₇ requires C, 61.81; H, 4.24%.

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References

1. T. H. SIMPSON and J. L. BERTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 4065.
2. L. JURD, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 1294.
3. S. MAHEY, S. K. MUKHERJEE and T. R. SESHADRI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 1052.
4. T. J. MABRY, K. R. MARKHAM and M. B. THOMAS, "The Systematic Identification of Flavonoids", Springer Verlag, N. Y., 1970.
5. C. A. HENRICK and P. R. JEFFERIES, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1964, 17, 984.
6. A. B. RAY, S. O. DUTTA and S. DASGUPTA, *Phytochemistry*, 1976, 15, 1797.
7. G. BERTI, O. LIVI, D. SEGNI and I. CAVERO, *Tetrahedron*, 1967, 23, 2295.
8. F. E. KING, T. J. KING and K. SELLARS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 92.
9. I. HEILBRON, A. H. COOK, H. M. BUNBURY and D. H. HEY, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", Eyre and Spottiswood, London, 1965, Vol. 3, p. 1711.
10. I. HEILBRON, A. H. COOK, H. M. BUNBURY and D. H. HEY, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", Eyre and Spottiswood, London, 1965, Vol. 5, p. 2832.
11. G. B. MARINI-BETTOLO, V. DELOPERU and E. HUG, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1950, 80, 63.

Thiocarbamide as Dealkylating Agent : Debenzylation of Certain 2-S-Benzyl- 1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets with Thiocarbamide

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APLICATION of thiocarbamide as debenzylating agent for 1-aryl-S-benzyl isothiocarbamides in acid medium was reported earlier¹. It is of interest to investigate this debenzylation reaction in other S-benzylated thioamido systems like 2-S-benzyl-1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (I). With this end in view, debenzylations of I have been attempted in basic and acidic conditions. No debenzylation is observed in acid medium. However, smooth debenzylation reaction of I is observed in presence of a tertiary base like pyridine. The present note describes these observations.

The debenzylation reaction of 2-S-benzyl-1,5-diphenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (Ia) with thiocarbamide in presence of pyridine in boiling ethanolic medium

affords a product, m.p. 143°. Elimination of hydrogen sulphide is not observed during the reaction. The product is desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. On pyrolysis, it gives a distinct odour of phenyl isothiocyanate. The ir spectrum of the product clearly indicates the presence of $\nu(\text{NH})$ (3300 cm⁻¹), $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ (1210 cm⁻¹) and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ (705 cm⁻¹) bands². No depression in melting point is observed when it is mixed with an authentic sample of 1,5-diphenyl-2,4-dithiobiuret (IIa)³. On the basis of all these facts, the product with m.p. 143° has been assigned structure IIa. In this reaction, S-benzyl isothiocarbamide (III) has been isolated as its picrate derivative, m.p. 181°.

Other 2-S-benzyl-1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (Ib and Ic) also get debenzylated into the related 1,5-diaryl-2,4-dithiobiurets (IIb and IIc) under analogous reaction conditions.

where R = (a) phenyl, (b) *p*-chlorophenyl and (c) *m*-chlorophenyl and R' = phenyl.

Experimental

The required 2-S-benzyl-1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (I) have been prepared by the interaction of 1-aryl-S-benzyl isothiocarbamides⁴ and aryl isothiocyanates by a known procedure⁵ (Ib, m.p. 120° and Ic, m.p. 102° have been prepared for the first time).

Debenzylation of 2-S-benzyl-1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (I); Formation of 1,5-diaryl-2,4-dithiobiurets (II): Details of a typical experiment (where aryl = phenyl) are as follows:

2-S-benzyl-1,5-diphenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (Ia, 2g) is suspended in ethanol (20 ml) and thiocarbamide (0.4 g) and pyridine (1 ml) are added to this. The reaction mixture is refluxed for 3 hr. Neither hydrogen sulphide nor benzyl mercaptan is eliminated. The reaction mixture is then cooled and acidified with dilute aqueous hydrochloric acid when an oily mass is obtained. The clear supernatant liquid is decanted off and to this is added an aqueous solution of picric acid when a yellow product is obtained. This is filtered and crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 181°. It is identified as the picrate of S-benzyl isothiocarbamide (III).

The oily mass is washed thoroughly with water and then triturated several times with petroleum ether followed by ethanol when a yellow solid

(1.7 g) is obtained. It is crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 143° (Found: N, 14.93; S, 22.53. $C_{14}H_{13}N_2S_2$ requires N, 14.63; S, 22.30%). This has been identified as 1,5-diphenyl-2,4-dithiobiuret (IIa) on the basis of m.m.p. with an authentic sample⁸.

When the debenzylations of other 2-S-benzyl-1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (Ib and Ic) were carried out with thiocarbamide in presence of pyridine in an ethanolic medium, the related products were obtained (IIb, m.p. 156°; Found: N, 13.56; S, 19.25. $C_{14}H_{13}N_2S_2Cl$ requires N, 13.06; S, 19.91% and IIc, m.p. 145°; Found: N, 13.26; S, 20.34. $C_{14}H_{13}N_2S_2Cl$ requires N, 13.06; S, 19.91%).

References

1. V. K. VERMA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 116.
2. N. B. COLTHUP, L. H. DALY and S. E. WIBERLEY, "Introduction to Infrared and Raman Spectroscopy", Academic Press, New York, 1964.
3. S. N. DIXIT, "Contribution to the Chemistry of Dithiobiurets, Dithiazolidines, the Related Formamidinothiocarbamides and Cyanothiocarbamides and Thiazolidines", Ph.D. Thesis, Banaras Hindu University, 1962.
4. WERNER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1890, 57, 295.
5. S. N. DIXIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 39, 407.

Some Interesting Reactions of N-Phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl Chloride

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CHEMISTRY of N-phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (I) with special reference to its application as an important intermediate in heterocyclic synthesis has been exhaustively investigated in this laboratory. The present note describes the intramolecular reaction of I in presence of anhydrous aluminium trichloride and intermolecular reaction in presence of aqueous ethanol and mixture of chloroform and aqueous ethanol in different proportions.

When N-phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride is boiled with anhydrous aluminium trichloride in dry diethyl ether medium for 4 hr evolution of hydrogen chloride is observed. The reaction mixture on fractional distillation gives an oily product, b.p. 248°. It is identified as 2-chlorobenzothiazole (II) on the basis of its reaction with phenyl thiocarbamide in acetone medium when 1-(phenylformamidino)-1-phenyl thiocarbamide hydrochloride (III), m.p. 158° is isolated¹. The formation of 2-chlorobenzothiazole (II) may be explained as follows:

When rectified spirit is added to a chilled N-phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (I) solution with stirring, a pale yellow solid, m.p. 118° is obtained. It is identified as 3-oxo-4-phenyl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (IV) on the basis of m.m.p. with an authentic sample⁸.

When the same reaction of I is carried out with a mixture of chloroform and rectified spirit (1:1, v/v), only IV is obtained. However, the reaction of I with a mixture of chloroform and rectified spirit (2:1, v/v) gives IV and also 5-oxo-4-phenyl-2-phenylimino-1,3,4-dithiazolidine (V). The latter has been identified on the basis of m.m.p. with an authentic sample⁸. As the ratio of chloroform in the mixture of chloroform and rectified spirit is increased, (3:1, v/v), V is formed almost exclusively. The IV and V may form as shown below.